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Development and Validation of Spectroscopic Method for Simultaneous Estimation of Acebrophylline and Montelukast Sodium in Combined Dosage Form

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ABSTRACT

A novel combination of Acebrophylline and Montelukast Sodium is used in the treatment of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) and bronchial asthma. A simple, sensitive, accurate and reproducible spectroscopic method has been developed and validated for the simultaneous estimation of Acebrophylline and Montelukast Sodium by solving of simultaneous equations (Vierodt's method). Acebrophylline and Montelukast Sodium were found to have absorbance maxima at 313 and 344.5 nm respectively in methanol. The method obeys Beer's law in the concentration range of 20-140 µg/ml ($R^2 = 0.9997$) for Acebrophylline and 1-7 µg/ml ($R^2 = 0.9993$) for Montelukast sodium. The LOD and LOQ were found to be 2.46µg/ml and 7.45µg/ml for Acebrophylline and 0.22µg/ml and 0.68µg/ml for Montelukast Sodium respectively. The recovery of Acebrophylline and Montelukast Sodium were found to be 99.57% and 100.78% respectively showing accuracy of the method. The assay of marketed tablet formulation (Abrofyl-M) was found to be 99.41% and 102.26% for Acebrophylline and Montelukast Sodium respectively. The method was validated statistically as per ICH guidelines. The method showed good reproducibility and recovery with % RSD less than 2. So, the proposed method was found to be simple, specific, precise, accuracy, linear, and robust. Hence it can be applied for routine analysis of Acebrophylline and Montelukast Sodium in pharmaceutical formulations.

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Introduction

Acebrophylline (ACBR), 1,2,3,6-tetrahydro-1,3-dimethyl-2,6-dioxo-7H-purine-7-acetic acid compd. with trans-4-[[[(2-amino-3,5-dibromophenyl)methyl]amino]cyclohexanol] is the salt obtained by reaction of equimolar amounts of theophylline-7-acetic acid, a xanthine derivative with specific bronchodilator activity and ambroxol, a mucolytic and expectorant. It is a novel drug with bronchodilating, anti-inflammatory and mucoregulating effect due to inhibition of phospholipase A, and phosphatidylcholine. Montelukast sodium (MTKT), [R-(E)]-1-[[[1-[3-[2-(7-chloroquinolinyl) ethenyl] phenyl]-3-[2-(1-hydroxy-1-methylethyl) phenyl] propyl] thio] methyl] cyclopropane acetic acid, monosodium salt is a selective and orally active leukotriene receptor antagonist that inhibits the cysteinyl leukotriene CysLT1 receptor. Leukotrienes cause narrowing and swelling of airways in lungs and also cause allergy symptoms (figure 1 & 2). By blocking leukotrienes, improves asthma symptoms, help to control asthma and improves seasonal allergy symptoms.¹⁻⁶ The combination of these two drugs are available in the market for the treatment of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) and bronchial asthma and also clinical trials has been reported for this combination in India.^{7,8} The review of literature revealed that several methods are available for the determination of acebrophylline and montelukast sodium individually. Reported method for estimation Acebrophylline in dosage form are spectrophotometry^{9,10}, RP-HPLC^{11,12} and HPTLC¹³ and similarly for estimation of Montelukast sodium in dosage form are spectrophotometry¹⁴⁻¹⁶, spectrofluorometry¹⁷, Voltammetric¹⁸, RP-HPLC¹⁹⁻²² and HPTLC²³⁻²⁵. But, there is no any analytical method has been reported yet for combination of these drugs. There for the present research work aims to develop a simple, sensitive, accurate and reproducible method for simultaneous estimation of Acebrophylline and Montelukast sodium in combined dosage form by spectrophotometric method.

Figure 1: Structural of Acebrophylline

Figure 2: Structural of Montelukast sodium

MATERIALS AND METHOD

The pure drug Acebrophylline was obtained as a gift sample from Ami life science Pvt. Ltd. Baroda, and the pure montelukast sodium was obtained as a gift sample from Cadila Pharmaceutical, Ahmedabad. Methanol of AR grade was purchased from Rankem (RFCL limited) New Delhi. Formulation ABROFYL- M tablet (Acebrophylline- 200 mg, Montelukast sodium- 10 mg). The spectrophotometer used was Shimadzu UV Visible spectrophotometer 2450 model with spectral bandwidth of 0.5 nm and wavelength accuracy (with automatic wavelength correction) of ± 0.3 nm. All the apparatus and instruments used were calibrated and validated.

Table 1: Optical parameters and Regression characteristic for ACBR and MTKT

Parameters	ACBR		MTKT	
Wavelength (nm)	313 nm	344.5 nm	313 nm	344.5 nm
Beer's law limit ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	20-140	20-140	1-7	1-7
Sandell's sensitivity ($\mu\text{g/cm}^2/0.001$ absorbance unit)	0.0408	0.0449	3.0737	0.2217
Regression equation	$Y = 0.0046x - 0.0031$	$Y = 0.0002x + 0.0021$	$Y = 0.0215x + 0.0008$	$Y = 0.0256x - 0.0020$
Standard Deviation of Slope*	0.0001	0.0002	0.0004	0.0006
Standard Deviation of Intercept*	0.0034	0.0017	0.0027	0.0017
Correlation coefficient (r^2)	0.9997	0.9997	0.9990	0.9993

*Standard Deviation of six determinations. ACBR: Acebrophylline, MTKT: Montelukast Sodium

Methodology

Preparation of Calibration Curve:

The stock standard solutions of ACBR and MTKT were prepared by dissolving 10 mg each of Acebrophylline and Montelukast Sodium in methanol separately and final volume was adjusted with same solvent in 100 ml of volumetric flask to get strength of 100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of each. Further solutions of a concentration range of 20-140 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for ACBR and 1-7 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for MTKT drug were prepared. A calibration curve was constructed and regression equation was obtained for each drug (Table 1). Absorption spectra of the standard solutions were recorded over the range of 200-400 nm then absorbance of the solutions was measured at 313nm for ACBR and 344.5nm for MTKT respectively.

Preparation of Sample Solution and Formulation Analysis

Twenty tablets were weighed accurately and a quantity of tablet powder equivalent to 10 mg was transferred to 100 ml volumetric flask, 80 ml of methanol was added to the same flask, sonicated for 5 min and diluted to 100 ml with methanol and filtered through Whatman filter paper No. 41. Resulting solution was further diluted with methanol to obtain solution having concentration 40 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and 2 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of ACBR and MTKT respectively. The sample solution was scanned in the wavelength range of 400–200 nm and measured the absorbance at 313nm and 344.5nm for ACBR and MTKT respectively. The % drug found was calculated on basis of simultaneous equation.

Figure 3: Linearity Spectra of Acebrophylline

Figure 4: Linearity Spectra of Montelukast Sodium

Figure 5: Calibration curve of Acebrophylline

Figure 6: Calibration curve of Montelukast Sodium

Simultaneous equation method²⁶

The absorptivity values of the drugs were determined at λ_{max} of ACBR and MTKT. The absorptivity value of the drugs is the ratio of absorbance at selected wavelengths with the concentration of drugs in $\mu\text{g/ml}$. A set of two simultaneous equations were framed using these absorptivity values.

$$A_1 = 0.004603 C_{ACBR} + 0.021665 C_{MTKT} \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

$$A_2 = 0.000209 C_{ACBR} + 0.024859 C_{MTKT} \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

Where, A_1 and A_2 are the absorbance of the test sample solution at 213 nm and 244.5 nm respectively.
 0.004603 And 0.000209 are absorptivities of ACBR at 213 nm and 244.5 nm respectively.
 0.021665 And 0.024859 are absorptivities of MTKT at 213 nm and 244.5 nm respectively.
 C_{ACBR} is the concentration of ACBR and C_{MTKT} is the concentration of MTKT in $\mu\text{g/ml}$.

Validation Parameter of the Developed Methods²⁷

Validation of the developed method was carried out as per ICH Q2 (R1) guidelines. Parameter such as linearity, accuracy, precision, LODs and LOQs were taken up as tests for method validation.

Linearity

For quantitative analysis of ACBR and MTKT and the linearity curve was plotted. Linearity range of ACBR and MTKT was established in concentration range of 20-140 µg/ml and 1-7 µg/ml respectively. The slope and intercept along with its correlation coefficient is given in Figure-3-6.

Recovery studies

Accuracy of the method was determined in terms of % recovery of standard. Recovery studies were carried out by addition of standard drug solution at the level of 80%, 100% and 120% to the pre-analyzed sample. Results of the recovery study were found to be within the acceptance criteria 100±10 %, indicating a good degree of sensitivity of the method towards detection of analytes in sample. In this method the known concentration standard drug was added to the assay sample. The amount present was calculated and the assay amount was reduced from it, which gives the amount recovered. The average percentage recoveries for ACBR and MTKT were obtained are shown in Table .2

Figure 3: Linearity Spectra of Acebrophylline

Figure 4: Linearity Spectra of Montelukast Sodium

Table 2: Result of Recovery Studies

Sr. No	Level Of Spikin g	Amount Taken (µg/ml)		Amount Added (µg/ml)		Total Amount (µg/ml)		% Recovery*± SD#		Mean Of % Recovery ± SD#	
		ACB R	MTK T	ACB R	MTK T	ACB R	MTK T	ACBR	MTKT	ACB R	MTK T
1	80%	40	2	32	1.6	72	3.6	99.38 ± 0.29	101.4 ± 1.22		
2	100%	40	2	40	2	80	4	99.53 ± 0.49	100.9 ± 1.00	99.57 ± 0.21	100.7 ± 0.73
3	120%	40	2	48	2.4	88	4.4	99.80 ± 0.35	99.99 ± 0.53		

*Average of three determinations. #SD: Standard Deviation of three determinations.

Precision: The intra-day and inter-day variations for determination of ACBR and MTKT were carried out three times in the same day and three consecutive days and % RSD were calculated. The method was found to be precise due to low values of the %RSD. (Table 3)

Table 3: Inter-day and Intra-day precision

Inter-day						Intra-day						
Amount taken ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)		Amount found ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)*		%RSD [#]		Amount taken ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)		Amount found ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)*		%RSD [#]		
ACB	MTK	ACB	MTK	ACB	MTK	AC	MT	ACB	MTK	ACB	MT	
R	T	R	T	R	T	BR	KT	R	T	R	KT	
20	1	20.3	0.99	0.87	1.00	20	1	20.26	1.05	0.86	1.90	
		3										
80	4	79.6	3.97	0.56	0.50	80	4	80.45	4.00	0.58	0.50	
		6										
140	7	140.	6.90	0.26	0.50	140	7	140.59	6.96	0.13	0.25	
		81										
				0.56	0.666					Mean	0.522	0.882
		Mean		22	4							
				0.30	0.289					SD	0.371	0.892
		SD		43	9							

*Average of three determination. [#]RSD: Relative Standard Deviation.

*Average of three determination.

LODs and LOQs

The LODs and LOQs of developed method were studied as per ICH guidelines. Several approaches for determining the LODs & LOQs are possible, depending on the procedure i.e a non-instrumental or instrumental.

$$\text{LODs} = 3.3 \sigma/S$$

$$\text{LOQs} = 10 \sigma/S$$

Where σ = the standard deviation of response and

S = the slope of calibration curve. The results obtained are shown in Table 5.

Robustness

The robustness was studied by analyzing the same samples ACBR and MTKT by deliberate variation in the method parameters. The change in the responses of ACBR and MTKT were noted. Robustness of the method was studied by changing the apparatus, analyst and instrument.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Overlay spectra of ACBR and MTKT (Fig. 7) shows that the estimation of both the drug can be possible using simultaneous equation method at the wavelength of 313nm and 344.5nm. Using appropriate dilutions of standard stock solution, the two solutions were scanned separately. A critical evaluation of proposed method was performed by statistical analysis of data where slope, intercept, correlation coefficient were studied. Beer's law is obeyed in the concentration range 20-140 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and 1-7 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and correlation coefficient of 0.9997 and 0.9993 for ACBR and MTKT respectively. The LOD and LOQ were found to be 2.4589 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and 7.4512 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for Acebrophylline and 0.2233 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and 0.6766 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for Montelukast Sodium respectively. The proposed method was also evaluated by the assay of commercially available tablets containing ACBR and MTKT ($n = 3$). The % assay was found to be 99.41% for ACBR and 102.26 % for MTKT (Table 4).

Table 4: Result of formulation analysis

Formulation	Label Claim		Amount Found*		% Assay \pm SD	
	ACBR (mg)	MTKT (mg)	ACBR (mg)	MTKT (mg)	ACBR	MTKT
ABROFYL - M	200	10	198.82 \pm 1.00	10.22 \pm 0.022	99.41 \pm 0.5	102.26 \pm 0.41

Further the precision of the method was confirmed by the inter-day and intra-day analysis. The % RSD of inter-day and intra-day precision was found to be 0.5622 and 0.5221 for ACBR and 0.6664 and 0.8822 for MTKT respectively. It indicates that the method has good precision. For ACBR, the recovery study results ranged from 99.38% to 99.80% with % RSD value is 0.2150% and for MTKT, the recovery results ranged from 99.99% to 101.42%, with % RSD value is 0.7204%. Hence, the accuracy of the method was confirmed. Also the robustness of the method has been established by changing the apparatus, analyst and instrument. The accuracy and reproducibility is evident from the data as results are close to 100 % and standard deviation is low.

Figure 7: Overlay spectra of ACBR & MTKT (40:2 $\mu\text{g/ml}$)

Table 5: Summary of Validation Parameters

Parameters	Result	
	ACBR	MTKT
Linearity Range($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	20-140	1-7
Accuracy		
(%Recovery \pm SD)	99.57 \pm 0.21	100.78 \pm 0.73
Precision (%RSD \pmSD)		
Inter-day (n=3)	0.5622 \pm 0.3043	0.6664 \pm 0.2899
Intra-day (n=3)	0.5221 \pm 0.3717	0.8822 \pm 0.8931
Limit Of Detection ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	2.4589	0.2233
Limit Of Quantification ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	7.4512	0.6766
Robustness(%RSD)		
By Changing Apparatus	1.5580	1.6950
By Changing Analyst	1.6024	1.7095
By Changing Instrument	1.9820	1.8895

CONCLUSION: The proposed spectroscopic method involving the simultaneous equation (vierodt's method) provides simple, accurate, fast and reproducible quantitative analysis for simultaneous determination of ACBR and MTKT in tablets. It can be successfully applied for simultaneous estimation of ACBR and MTKT in tablet dosage forms without prior separation and any interference in quality control.

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